

ASPECTS OF CREATING A POSITIVE ENVIRONMENT IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Abstract. *This article highlights the issues of effective organization of creating a positive environment in the educational process and the application of optimal approaches in this regard. Factors, principles and tools affecting the creation of a positive environment in the educational process are systematized. The importance of creating a positive environment in the qualitative improvement of the effectiveness of education is analyzed. It also tells about educational methods that serve to create a positive atmosphere in the audience and their improvement.*

Keywords: *environment in the educational process, methods oriented to the educational environment, pedagogical environment, motivational environment, differential approach.*

АСПЕКТЫ СОЗДАНИЯ ПОЗИТИВНОЙ СРЕДЫ В ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОМ ПРОЦЕССЕ

Аннотация. *В данной статье освещены вопросы эффективной организации создания позитивной среды в образовательном процессе и применения оптимальных подходов в этом отношении. Систематизированы факторы, принципы и инструменты, влияющие на создание позитивной атмосфере в образовательном процессе. Анализируется важность создания позитивной среды в качественном повышении эффективности образования. Также рассказывается о воспитательных методах, служащих для создания положительной атмосферы в аудитории и их оздоровления.*

Ключевые слова: *среда в образовательном процессе, методы возникающие на среду образования, педагогическая среда, мотивационная среда, дифференцированный подход.*

INTRODUCTION

Lifelong education - is continuous learning and exploration in response to changing contexts. It involves the process of reflection, analysis and implementation. Reflection is necessary to think critically in the implementation of the process, taking into account different points of view, departing from known or accepted knowledge. Reasoning mobilizes cognitive skills such as analytical or critical thinking to anticipate what changes may occur in the future or what the consequences of actions taken today may be. Both critical thinking and reasoning contribute to a person's willingness to act responsibly. Whether the educational environment is positive or negative increases the value of learning outcomes

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the current era of globalization, the scope of information flow has expanded. This causes a number of complications in working with learners. In the world surrounding the learner, there are information flows that can negatively and positively affect the development of a person in different directions. Among the basic professional competence of today's educator, we can include the component of being able to bring the learner surrounded by various information

flows into the educational environment and ensure his activity in this environment. This, in turn, creates a problem for educators to create a positive environment in the educational process.

RESULTS

The environment in the educational process results from the personal and professional qualities of educators and learners. Each participant of the educational process has his own personal environment, that is, aura. In turn, the organized educational process is under a certain environment too. A certain degree of relationship is formed between these two objects. Several factors influence the positive interaction of this relationship. We have systematized several types of these factors. (Figure 1)

Figure 1.

Psychological factors: The psychological state and interaction of the participants of the educational process was considered the main factor of education at any time. There are a number of psychological approaches that can be applied to the educational process. These include biological, behavioral, humanistic, process-based, cognitive, social-psychological, psycho-analytical approaches. It is very important for the teacher to be able to choose the appropriate psychological approach to the process in the formation of positive dynamics in students.

Another effect of psychological factors is reflected in the motivational part of education. Correctly chosen motivation determines the effectiveness of the educational process. The effectiveness of the educational environment relies on the skillful performance of the role of "Motivator" by the teacher. Promotion of motivational ideas aimed at the personal development of learners and stabilization of human capital and penetration into the psychological aura of learners are important aspects of this process.[5]

Pedagogical factors. Regardless of whether the teacher works as a pedagogue, adrologue or tutor in the educational process, he works based on the views and professional competences of the professional qualities of the pedagogue. Optimizing professional qualities and professional competence will not fail to have a positive effect on the educational environment.

The teacher's correct approach to conflict situations, stability to internal and external psychological influences are among them. Conducting the educational process on the basis of democratic principles such as transparency, openness, equal rights, integrity, continuity, and flexibility will undoubtedly create a positive atmosphere in the audience. A teacher's cold-hearted approach to these and other principles has a negative effect on the morale of learners. A single plot, an unfairly organized assessment process creates a feeling of discontent among students and in turn leads to a negative direction of the educational environment. Therefore, personal and professional development of the teacher is the main aspect of education.[4]

DISCUSSION

In general, today's teacher should appear as a facilitator in the educational process. These are skills related to achieving goals and working with other people in everyday situations, as well as managing one's emotions. They include personal characteristics such as determination to achieve a goal, empathic ability to focus, ethical behavior, courage to make leadership decisions. In this way, independent thinking, individual and collective development, protection and implementation of ideas are developed. In the management of the audience, the right approach to the environment, the ability to correctly direct management methods such as authoritarianism, democracy and liberality, also embody the principles of professional qualities.

Didactic factors. The main emphasis of pedagogical conditions is necessarily proportional to the variety and attractiveness of didactic materials. This accelerates the process of adaptation of the teacher to the audience. In addition, continuously improving didactic provision increases the interest of learners in learning, as well as expands the range of individual possibilities of learning. If the learner has the opportunity to work with the didactic material in a form suitable for him or if he is given a choice in the assessment materials, he will feel satisfied with the education and, of course, the need to receive education in a positive mood will appear.

Correctly selected educational technologies and methods form a positive educational environment. The era of globalization requires the movement and development of society as a whole. Innovation is now rarely the product of individual human efforts, but rather the result of how we acquire and apply knowledge, how we share and integrate ideas. It is desirable that the methods and technologies used in the educational process today can direct the individual potential of learners to collective action.

Researcher A. Schleicher believes that the well-being of society depends more on the ability of people to act collectively. It refers to teaching and encouraging collaboration to enhance individual academic achievement that enables the learner to think about their own tasks, act both for and with others.[3]

Organizational factors . As organizational factors, it is possible to emphasize the equipment of the auditorium, the proper provision of the material and technical base, and in general, the existence of favorable conditions for the learner. This view is especially important for practical training.

It is known that the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Education contains standards for the organizational aspects of the educational process, as well as state educational requirements and other normative documents related to education. A creative approach to organizational work without deviating from normative requirements has a positive effect on the educational environment.[1] [2] Correctly selected colors, graphics, exhibition materials in an optimal-motivational nature will make the process environment positive. In this case, the

improvement of the general requirements for the organization of education based on the ideas of convergence leads to a qualitative change of the organizational factors. That is, the geographical location of the object where the educational process is organized, the economic and social situation, in a way that is harmonized with the values of the population.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, we can emphasize that the scope of factors affecting the educational environment is wide. We touched on some of them in this article. But the need for continuous research in this field is proportional to efforts to increase the effectiveness of education. Because organizational processes that are coordinated with the interest, passion, and needs of learners can bring positive changes to educational results. Regardless of whether education is organized in the classroom or outside the classroom, striving to create a positive environment in the process remains one of the important aspects of the organization of quality education.

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